

Software Testing Techniques and Strategies

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Abstract

This paper describes Software testing, need for software testing, Software testing goals and principles. Further it describe about different Software testing techniques and different software testing strategies. Finally it describes the difference between software testing and debugging.

Keywords— Debugging, Software Testing Goals, Software Testing principles, Software Testing Techniques, Software Testing strategies

I. INTRODUCTION

Software testing refers to process of evaluating the software with intention to find out error in it. Software testing is a technique aimed at evaluating an attribute or capability of a program or product and determining that it meets its quality. Software testing is also used to test the software for other software quality factors like reliability, usability, integrity, security, capability, efficiency, portability, maintainability, compatibility etc.

For many years now we are still using the same testing techniques .some of which is crafted method rather than good engineering methods. Testing can be costly but not testing software can be even more costly. Software testing aims at achieving certain a goals and principles which are to be followed.

1.1. Need for Software testing

Software development involves developing software against a set of requirements. Software testing is needed to verify and validate that the software that has been built has been built to meet these specifications. If not we may probably loose our client. So in order to make it sure, that we provide our client a proper software solution, we go for testing [1]. Testing ensures that what you get in the end is what you wanted to build. We check out if there is any problem, any error in the system, which can make software unusable by the client. This helps in the prevention of errors in a system.

1.2. Goals for software testing

Goals are the output of the software process. Software testing has following goals. [2]

1) Verification and validation

Testing can also be used for verifying that the product or the software works as desired and validate whether the software fulfills condition laid down

2) Priority Coverage

Testing should be performed in efficient and effective manner within the budget and schedule limits.

3) Balanced

Testing process must balance the requirements, technical limitation and user expectation.

4) Traceable

Documents should be prepared of both success and failures of testing process. So no need to test same thing again.

5) Deterministic

We should know what we are doing, what we are targeting, what will be the possible outcome.

1.3. Testing principles

Principle is the rule or method in action that has to be followed. Different testing principles are as follows: [2]

1) Test a program to try to make it fail

Testing is the process of executing a program with the intent of finding errors. We should expose failures to make testing process more effective.

2) Start testing early

This helps in fixing enormous errors in early stages of development, reduces the rework of finding the errors in the initial stages.

3) Testing is context dependant

Testing should be appropriate and different for different points of time.

4) Define Test Plan

Test Plan usually describes test scope, test objectives, test strategy, test environment, deliverables of the test, risks and mitigation, schedule, levels of testing to be applied, methods, techniques and tools to be used. Test plan should efficiently meet the needs of an organization and clients as well.

5) Design Effective Test cases

Test case must be specified in a way that is measurable so that testing results are unambiguous.

6) Test for valid as well as invalid Conditions

In addition to valid inputs, we should also test system for invalid and unexpected inputs/conditions

7) Testing must be done by different persons at different levels

Different purpose addressed at different level of testing so different person should perform testing differently using different testing techniques at different level.

8) End of Testing

Testing has to be stopped somewhere. The testing can be stopped when risk is under some limit or if there is limitation.

II. SOFTWARE TESTING TECHNIQUES

In this Section the focus is mainly on the different software testing Techniques.

Software Testing Techniques can be divided into two types:-

2.1. Manual testing (static testing)

It is a slow process and laborious where testing is done statically .It is done in early phase of life cycle. It is also called static testing. It is done by analyst, developer and testing team.

Different Manual testing Techniques are as follows:-

- A) walk through
- B) Informal Review
- C) Technical Review
- D) Inspection

2.2. Automated Testing (Dynamic testing)

In this tester runs the script on the testing tool and testing is done. Automated testing is also called dynamic testing. Automated testing is further classified into four types

- A) Correctness testing
- B) Performance testing
- C) Reliability testing
- D) Security testing

Fig 1:-Further classification of Automated software Testing

2.2.1. Correctness Testing

Correctness is the minimum requirement of software. Correctness testing will need some type of oracle, to tell the right behaviour from the wrong one. The tester may or may not know the inside details of the software module under test. [3] Therefore either white box testing or black box testing can be used.

Correctness testing has following three forms:-

- 1) White box testing
- 2) Black box testing
- 3) Grey box testing

Fig 2:- Different form of Correctness testing [3]

1) White box testing

White box testing is highly effective in detecting and resolving problems, because bugs can often be found before they cause trouble.[5] White box testing is the process of giving the input to the system and checking how the system processes that input to generate the required output. White box testing is also called white box analysis, clear box testing or clear box analysis.[5] White box testing is applicable at integration, unit and system levels of the software testing process.[3] White box testing is considered as a *security testing* method that can be used to validate whether code implementation follows intended design, to validate implemented security functionality, and to uncover exploitable vulnerabilities.

Some Different types of white box testing techniques are as follows:-

- 1) Basis Path Testing
- 2) Loop Testing
- 3) Control Structure Testing

Advantages of white box testing:-

- 1) All independent paths in a module will be exercised at least once.
- 2) All logical decisions will be exercised.
- 3) All loops at their boundaries will be executed.
- 4) Internal data structures will be exercised to maintain their validity.
- 5) Errors in hidden codes are revealed.
- 6) Approximate the partitioning done by execution equivalence.
- 7) Developer carefully gives reason about implementation.

Disadvantages of white box testing:-

- 1) Missed out the cases omitted in the code.
- 2) As knowledge of code and internal structure is a prerequisite, a skilled tester is needed to carry out this type of testing, which increases the cost.
- 3) And it is nearly impossible to look into every bit of code to find out hidden errors, which may create problems, resulting in failure of the application.

2) Black box testing

Black box testing is testing software based on output requirements and without any knowledge of the internal structure or coding in the program.[5]

Basically Black box testing is an integral part of 'Correctness testing' but its ideas are not limited to correctness testing only. The goal is to test how well the component conforms to the published requirement for the component. Black box testing have little or no regard to the internal logical structure of the system, it only examines the fundamental aspect of the system. It makes sure that input is properly accepted and output is correctly produced. [3]

Some Different types of Black box testing techniques are as follows:-

- 1) Equivalent Partitioning
- 2) Boundary value Analysis
- 3) Cause-Effect Graphing Techniques
- 4) Comparison Testing
- 5) Fuzz Testing
- 6) Model-based testing

Advantages of Black box testing:-

- 1) The number of test cases are reduced to achieve reasonable testing
- 2) The test cases can show presence or absence of classes of errors.
- 3) Black box tester has no "bond" with the code.
- 4) Programmer and tester both are independent of each other.
- 5) More effective on larger units of code than clear box testing.

Disadvantages of Black box testing:-

- 1) Test cases are hard to design without clear specifications.
- 2) Only small numbers of possible input can actually be tested.
- 3) Some parts of the back end are not tested at all.
- 4) Chances of having unidentified paths during this testing
- 5) Chances of having repetition of tests that are already done by programmer

3) Grey box testing

The Graybox Testing Methodology is a software testing method used to test software applications. The methodology is platform and language independent. The current implementation of the Graybox methodology is heavily dependent on the use of a host platform debugger to execute and validate the software under test. Recent studies have confirmed that the Graybox method can be applied in real time using software executing on the target platform.

Grey box testing techniques combined the testing methodology of white box and black box. Grey box testing technique is used for testing a piece of software against its specifications but using some knowledge of its internal working as well. The understanding of internals of the program in grey box testing is more than black box testing, but less than clear box testing. [3]

The Graybox methodology is a ten step process for testing computer software.

Ten Step Graybox Methodology

- 1) Identify Inputs
- 2) Identify Outputs
- 3) Identify Major Paths
- 4) Identify Subfunction (SF)X
- 5) Develop Inputs for SF X
- 6) Develop Outputs for SF X

- 7) Execute Test Case for SF X
- 8) Verify Correct Result for SF X
- 9) Repeat Steps 4:8 for other SF
- 10) Repeat Steps 7&8 for Regression

The Graybox methodology utilizes automated software testing tools to facilitate the generation of test unique software. Module drivers and stubs are created by the toolset to relieve the software test engineer from having to manually generate this code. The toolset also verifies code coverage by instrumenting the test code. "Instrumentation tools help with the insertion of instrumentation code without incurring the bugs that would occur from manual instrumentation".

By operating in a debugger or target emulator, the Graybox toolset controlled the operation of the test software. The Graybox methodology has moved out of a debugger into the real world and into real-time. The methodology can be applied in real-time by modifying the basic premise that inputs can be sent to the test software via normal system messages and outputs are then verified using the system output messages.

2.2.2. PERFORMANCE TESTING

Performance Testing involve all the phases as the mainstream testing life cycle as an independent discipline which involve strategy such as plan, design, execution, analysis and reporting. [3]

Not all software has specification on performance explicitly. But every system will have implicit performance requirements.

Performance has always been a great concern and driving force of computer evolution. The goals of performance testing can be performance bottleneck identification, performance comparison and evaluation.

By performance testing we can measure the characteristics of performance of any applications. One of the most important objectives of performance testing is to maintain a low latency of a website, high throughput and low utilization. [3]

Performance testing has two forms:-

Load testing

Load testing is the process of subjecting a computer, peripheral, server, network or application to a work level approaching the limits of its specifications. Load testing can be done under controlled lab conditions to compare the capabilities of different systems or to accurately measure the capabilities of a single system. In this we can check whether the software can handle the load of many user or not.

Stress testing

Stress testing is a testing, which is conducted to evaluate a system or component at or beyond the limits of its specified requirements to determine the load under which it fails and how. [3]

2.2.3. RELIABILITY TESTING

The purpose of reliability testing is to discover potential problems with the design as early as possible and, ultimately, provide confidence that the system meets its reliability requirements. Reliability testing is related to many aspects of software in which testing process is included; this testing process is an effective sampling method to measure software reliability. In system after software is developed reliability testing techniques like analyze or fix techniques can be carried out to check whether to use the software.

2.2.4. SECURITY TESTING

Software quality, reliability and security are tightly coupled. Flaws in software can be exploited by intruders to opens security holes.

Security testing makes sure that only the authorized personnel can access the program and only the authorized personnel can access the functions available to their security level. The security testing is performed to check whether there is any information leakage in the sense by encrypting the application or using wide range of software's and hardware's and firewall etc.

III. SOFTWARE TESTING STRATEGIES

A strategy for software Testing integrates software test case design methods into a well planned Series of steps that result in successful Construction of software that result in successful construction of software. Software testing Strategies gives the road map for testing. A software testing Strategy should be flexible enough to promote a customized testing approach at same time it must be right enough. Strategy is generally developed by project managers, software engineer and testing specialist.

There are four different software testing strategies.

- 1) Unit testing
- 2) Integration testing
- 3) Acceptance/Validation testing
- 4) System testing

3.1. Unit testing

Unit is the smallest module i.e. smallest collection of lines of code which can be tested. Unit testing is just one of the levels of testing which go together to make the big picture of testing a system. IT complements integration and system level testing. It should also complement code reviews and walkthroughs.

Unit testing is generally seen as a white box test class. That is it is biased to looking at and evaluating the code as implemented. Rather than evaluating conformance to some set of requirements.

Benefits of Unit Testing:-

- 1) Unit level testing is very cost effective.
- 2) It provides a much greater reliability improvement for resources expanded than system level testing. In

particular, it tends to reveal bugs which are otherwise insidious and are often catastrophic like the strange system crashes that occur in the field when something unusual happens.

- 3) Be able to test parts of a project without waiting for the other parts to be available,
- 4) Achieve parallelism in testing by being able to test and fix problems simultaneously by many engineers,
- 5) Be able to detect and remove defects at a much less cost compared to other later stages of testing,
- 6) Be able to take advantage of a number of formal testing techniques available for unit testing,
- 7) Simplify debugging by limiting to a small unit the possible code areas in which to search for bugs,
- 8) Be able to test internal conditions that are not easily reached by external inputs in the larger integrated systems
- 9) Be able to achieve a high level of structural coverage of the code,
- 10) Avoid lengthy compile-build-debug cycles when debugging difficult problems.

Unit testing techniques

A number of effective testing techniques are usable in unit testing stage. The testing techniques may be broadly divided into three types:

1. Functional Testing
2. Structural Testing
3. Heuristic or Intuitive Testing

3.2. Integration testing

Integration testing is a systematic technique for constructing the program structure while at the same time conducting tests to uncover errors associated with interfacing. The objective is to take unit tested components and build a program structure that has been dictated by design.

Different Integration testing Strategies are discussed below:-

- 1) Top down Integration testing
- 2) Bottom up Integration testing

Top down Integration

Top-down integration testing is an incremental approach to construct program structure. Modules are integrated by moving downward through the structure, beginning with the main control module. Modules subordinate to the main control module are incorporated into the structure in either a depth-first or breadth-first manner. [4]

The integration process is performed in a series of five steps:

1. The main control module is used as a test driver and stubs are substituted for all components directly subordinate to the main control module.

2. Depending on the integration approach selected subordinate stubs are replaced one at a time with actual components.

3. Tests are conducted as each component is integrated.

4. On completion of each set of tests, another stub is replaced with the real component.

5. Regression testing may be conducted to ensure that new errors have not been introduced.

It is not as relatively simple as it looks. In this logistic problem can arise. Problem arises when testing low level module which requires testing upper level. Stub replace low level module at the beginning of top down testing. So no data can flow in upward direction.

Bottom up Integration

Bottom-up integration testing, as its name implies, begins construction and testing with atomic modules. Because components are integrated from the bottom up, processing required for components subordinate to a given level is always available and the need for stubs is eliminated. [4]

A bottom-up integration strategy may be implemented with the following steps:

1. Low-level components are combined into clusters that perform a specific software subfunction.
2. A driver is written to coordinate test case input and output.
3. The cluster is tested.
4. Drivers are removed and clusters are combined moving upward in the program structure.

3.3. Acceptance testing

Acceptance testing (also known as user acceptance testing) is a type of testing carried out in order to verify if the product is developed as per the standards and specified criteria and meets all the requirements specified by customer. [4] This type of testing is generally carried out by a user/customer where the product is developed externally by another party.

Acceptance testing falls under black box testing methodology where the user is not very much interested in internal working/coding of the system, but evaluates the overall functioning of the system and compares it with the requirements specified by them. User acceptance testing is considered to be one of the most important testing by user before the system is finally delivered or handed over to the end user.

Acceptance testing is also known as validation testing, final testing, QA testing, factory acceptance testing and application testing etc. And in software engineering, acceptance testing may be carried out at two different levels; one at the system provider level and another at the end user level.

Types of Acceptance Testing

User Acceptance Testing

User acceptance testing in software engineering is considered to be an essential step before the system is finally accepted by the end user. In general terms, user acceptance testing is a process of testing the system before it is finally accepted by user.

Alpha Testing & Beta Testing

Alpha testing is a type of acceptance testing carried out at developer's site by users.[4] In this type of testing, the user goes on testing the system and the outcome is noted and observed by the developer simultaneously.

Beta testing is a type of testing done at user's site. The users provide their feedback to the developer for the outcome of testing. This type of testing is also known as field testing. Feedback from users is used to improve the system/product before it is released to other users/customers.

Operational Acceptance Testing

This type of testing is also known as operational readiness/preparedness testing. It is a process of ensuring all the required components (processes and procedures) of the system are in place in order to allow user/tester to use it.

Contact and Regulation Acceptance Testing

In contract and regulation acceptance testing, the system is tested against the specified criteria as mentioned in the contract document and also tested to check if it meets/obeys all the government and local authority regulations and laws and also all the basic standards.

3.4. System testing

System testing of software or hardware is testing conducted on a complete, integrated system to evaluate the system's compliance with its specified requirements. System testing falls within the scope of black box testing, and as such, should require no knowledge of the inner design of the code or logic. System testing is actually a series of different tests whose primary purpose is to fully exercise the computer-based system. Although each test has a different purpose, all work to verify that system elements have been properly integrated and perform allocated functions.

Some of Different types of system testing are as follows:-

1. Recovery testing
2. Security testing
3. graphical user interface testing
4. Compatibility testing

Recovery Testing

Recovery testing is a system test that forces the software to fail in a variety of ways and verifies that recovery is properly

performed. If recovery is automatic, re-initialization, check pointing mechanisms, data recovery, and restart are evaluated for correctness. If recovery requires human intervention, the mean-time-to-repair is evaluated to determine whether it is within acceptable limits.

Security testing

Security testing attempts to verify that protection mechanisms built into a system will, in fact, protect it from improper penetration.

During security testing, the tester plays the role(s) of the individual who desires to penetrate the system. Anything goes! The tester may attempt to acquire passwords through external clerical means; may attack the system with custom software designed to breakdown any defenses that have been constructed; may overwhelm the system, thereby denying service to others; may purposely cause system errors, hoping to penetrate during recovery; may browse through insecure data, hoping to find the key to system entry.

Graphical user interface testing

Graphical user interface testing is the process of testing a product's graphical user interface to ensure it meets its written specifications. This is normally done through the use of a variety of test cases.

Compatibility testing

Compatibility testing, part of software non-functional tests, is testing conducted on the application to evaluate the application's compatibility with the computing environment.

IV. DISCUSSION

In this section difference between testing and debugging is shown.

Software testing is a process that can be systematically planned and specified. Test case design can be conducted, a strategy can be defined, and results can be evaluated against prescribed expectations.

Debugging occurs as a consequence of successful testing. That is, when a test case uncovers an error, debugging is the process that results in the removal of the error.

The purpose of debugging is to locate and fix the offending code responsible for a symptom violating a known specification. Debugging typically happens during three activities in software development, and the level of granularity of the analysis required for locating the defect differs in these three.[1]

The first is during the coding process, when the programmer translates the design into an executable code. During this process the errors made by the programmer in writing the code can lead to defects that need to be quickly detected and fixed before the code goes to the next stages of development. Most often, the developer also performs unit testing to expose any defects at the module or component level.[1]

The second place for debugging is during the later stages of testing, involving multiple components or a complete system, when unexpected behavior such as wrong return codes or abnormal program termination may be found. A certain amount of debugging of the test execution is necessary to conclude that the program under test is the cause of the unexpected behavior.[1]

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper on Software testing describes in detail about software testing, need of software testing, Software testing goals and principles. . Software testing is often less formal and rigorous than it should, and a main reason for that is because we have struggled to define best practices, methodologies, principles, standards for optimal software testing. To perform testing effectively and efficiently, everyone involved with testing should be familiar with basic software testing goals, principles, limitations and concepts.

We further explains different Software testing techniques such as Correctness testing, Performance testing, Reliability testing, Security testing. Further we have discussed the basic principles of black box testing, white box testing and gray box testing. We have surveyed some of the strategies supporting these paradigms, and have discussed their pros and cons. We also describes about different software testing strategies such as unit testing, Integration testing, acceptance testing and system testing.

Finally there is comparison between debugging and testing. Testing is more than just debugging .Testing is not only used to locate defects and correct them it is also used in validation, verification process and measurement.

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